

THE FACTORS OF CONTINUOUS PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. *Individual abilities in a person emerge as a result of professional efficiency in society. Development is a long-term process and unfolds throughout person's life. This article discusses the demands placed on educators with changing times, self-improvement, self-development, especially the creation of a structure for success in professional activities. The analysis of the structure is explained with the scientific-theoretical views of experts and researchers.*

Keywords: *professional development, methodological basis, scientific-theoretical views, demand, relevance to profession.*

Introduction. The increasing discourse on the development of science, education, and economy demands a broader utilization of the professional skills and personal resources of all specialists. This necessitates the expansion and multifaceted utilization of the opportunities of psychological-pedagogical disciplines, their influence, and teaching methodologies in various spheres of human life. Today, the number of teachers who consider personal development and achieving success in life as essential for professional activity is increasing significantly. They are increasingly recognizing the need for psychological-pedagogical and methodological support. The demand for such support shapes the professional intentions, arises in the process of career choice, and remains integral throughout an individual's entire professional life.

RESEARCH AND INTERPRETATION. Collaborating with teachers in the realm of personal development isn't just about individual significance; it extends significantly to societal importance. This is because enhancing professional and psychological well-being, promoting self-expression, and ensuring support are all integral to increasing the effectiveness of professional activities, which are the fundamental characteristics of human activity: motivation, purpose, object, structure, and means. Below, we analyze some aspects of self-improvement and professional development through organization (Figure 1).

Professional activity is a societal activity that requires specialized knowledge, skills, abilities, and competencies, as well as personal characteristics identified in terms of professional qualities. Professional activity primarily involves work, and work is an activity aimed at achieving a specific goal according to a predetermined purpose. The main characteristic of work is its direction towards a specific goal. In the modern world, while some professions may disappear and new ones emerge, the need for the teaching profession continues to rise and evolve with each era.

ANALYSIS OF METHODOLOGICAL AND SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE. Professors Kh.Ibrahimov and M.Quronov define "...pedagogical activity as a unique type of work aimed at preparing the younger generation for life in accordance with spiritual, aesthetic, ethical, political, and economic goals" [3; p 29]. It means that, pedagogical activity encompasses all aspects of social life within its scope.

Figure 1. Factors of continuous professional development in self-improvement of teachers.

Similarly, in the "General Pedagogy" course by B.Mamurov, it is possible to find the following information related to Russian psychologist Y.A.Klimov: according to him, in the proposed classification, other people who are not teachers, i.e., individuals belonging to the "...human-to-human" type is included in the subject of pedagogical professional activity. Pedagogical activity is characterized by a high level of responsibility and sense of duty. One distinguishing aspect of pedagogical activity in the "...human-to-human" type, compared to other types of activities, is that it is considered both transformative and managerial at the same time. A teacher is responsible for shaping both the individual and collective aspects, aiding in their development on intellectual, emotional, and physical levels, and overseeing the process of formation and transformation. [4; 8-p.]

On January 25, 2021, the decree signed by our President regarding "Measures to Enhance Scientific Research Activities in the Field of Public Education and Establish a Continuous Professional Development System" [1] has opened up new opportunities for improving the skills of pedagogical staff and enhancing their professional development. According to the decree, a teaching system based on programs that promote skill development is being implemented. In this system, teachers are educated based on their level of skill, knowledge, scientific-pedagogical proficiency, psychological readiness, and work experience.

The purpose of continuous professional development for school pedagogical staff outlined in this decree is to ensure the constant improvement of their professional and pedagogical competence in the positions they hold, their specialization or subjects they teach. It emphasizes the continuous updating of their teaching skills, mastery of pedagogical and information technologies, as well as their pedagogical knowledge, skills, and methods, including interactive teaching methods, in line with state educational standards, requirements, and legislation in the field.

Additionally, the main tasks of continuous professional development include:

- creating an educational environment that provides ample opportunities for the ongoing professional development of staff.

- enhancing independent critical thinking skills and developing staff capabilities through the integration of independent thinking and the provision of new knowledge to foster independent work and the development of creative thinking skills.

- elevating the competency level and enhancing the professional skills of staff through the development of individual professional development trajectories.

- formulating practical skills in working with advanced pedagogical and information technologies.

- designating tasks such as enhancing the professional development, responsibility, engagement in scientific research, and fostering creative skills of staff as the main sources for improving the overall quality of education.

One of the most important tasks is to identify needs based on analyzing the results of the teacher's activities. Need - a necessary requirement for human existence and development. The need to express the necessity of human vital means is universal and permanent for all stages of development in the scientific category of progress. Its historical appearance in the conditions of market economy is a demanding concept. Distinguishing between demand and need, the independent economic category (in scientific terms) operates and extends only to the portion satisfied with money. Needs are divided into physical, realized, and unrealized types. Physical needs manifest as a desire to change one's workplace or living environment, realized needs indicate a willingness to purchase things that are available to us, while unrealized needs are psychological and are internal desires. [10; 115-p.]. In general, needs are those things that arise within a person (in the inner world) and are satisfied, and manifested in various forms, adequately and individually for each person at their own time [9]. The level of need intensity depends on the strength of motivation behind the goal.

The issue of economic development remained stagnant at the beginning of the 20th century because until that time, free labor market practices were not common. People's economic lives were constrained by traditional customs, as well as the patriarchal norms of society. The industrial revolution, however, brought about the emergence of labor markets and the development of new

professions. The majority of society faced the challenge of finding work and adapting to it professionally. The changing historical circumstances transformed the world of professions from top to bottom. New labor tools and equipment over the years have demanded skilled workers capable of performing work functions at a high level of quality and efficiency.

Under F.Taylor's system, the organization of labor underwent significant expansion. Apart from rationalizing labor operations, great importance was placed on the professional competence of the employee. During this period, the practice of free labor selection remained essential, and the new field of applied psychology—psycho-techniques emerged to address issues of self-determination and professional efficiency, thus contributing to the development of labor skills and addressing motivational matters. Psychological research delved deeply into the concepts of motive, motivation, and incentivization, which were crucial factors in professional development.

In psychology, particularly by S.L.Rubinshtein, the concept of motivation is taught based on how individuals interact socially in society, how they regulate themselves, and how their behavior evolves. Motivation is considered as the focal point of effective activity, and the need for significant engagement with it has further expanded the scope of this theory. When explaining the psychological nature of motivation, scholars have defined it as the source of human activity and the impetus behind it [11]. In this regard, it is possible to emphasize motivation as the foremost aspect of continuous professional development.

In considering the factors contributing to a teacher's professional development, two main distinctions arise within the process:

- 1) External conditions between the individual and life circumstances;
- 2) Intrapersonal factors.

The main contradiction defining an individual's development is explained by the presence of conflicts between the person's existing traits, virtues, and the objective requirements of professional activity. Its formation involves stages and functional developments, referred to as stage and functional development, which are carried out at a certain stage and lead to the accumulation of potential and the emergence of new elements in terms of their quality as factors that form a person's potential.

The professional development of a specialist involves the creation of internal potentials as a result of the active interaction between the individual and social-professional groups and means of labor.

Education, professional knowledge and skills, general and specific abilities, social significance, and important professional qualities shape the professional development capacity of a specialist. Bringing potential into play depends on several factors:

- the individual's biological-physical condition;
- social situation;
- the nature of professional activity;
- the person's activity;
- the individual's need for self-improvement and advancement;
- the presence of life goals.

However, the key factor in a teacher's professional development is the system of objective requirements that determine the emergence of new traits and qualities not determined by professional activity and the means to achieve them. Adjusting or redesigning the methods of implementation, as well as modifying the relationship with the main activity, determines the stages

of a teacher's development. In developing professional skills, social-economic conditions, social-professional groups, and the teacher's own activity are also important. Their subjective activity is determined by needs, motives, interests, directions, and other systems. Studying scientific literature shapes the qualities that enhance professional development, such as professional direction, competence, social significance, and professional skills, and identifies acceptable methods for their integration, preparing for continuous professional growth, and finding effective ways to improve and innovate in their activities. The process of professional development benefits from utilizing methods that demonstrate social influence, which should be applied in a timely manner to the individual. These methods include, but are not limited to, acquiring essential knowledge, skills, qualities, behaviors, and individual methods for professional development, as well as establishing activity systems tailored to various aspects of professional significance (cognitive, educational, professional, and others).

CONCLUSION. In general, a teacher must clearly define their own development strategy alongside playing a role in someone else's life, ensuring their own progress and simultaneously influencing the behavior of students in such a way as to cultivate them accordingly. The ongoing improvements in the educational system and skill development in our country reassure each educator with the opportunity to enhance their proficiency. In this context, the utilization of cognitive mechanisms in applying professional standards in practice plays a pivotal role in a teacher's professional development.

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